

Major Chemical Consituents of Essential Oil of *Ocimum sanctum*

Paper Id : 19273 Submission Date : 2024-09-15 Acceptance Date : 2024-09-23 Publication Date : 2024-09-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13989589

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Abstract The constituents of essential oil isolated by hydro distillation of leaf parts of *Ocimum sanctum* from Bharatpur , Rajasthan was examined by Gas chromatography and Mass spectroscopy. 43 compounds accounting for 99.9% of oil were identified in leaf oil. The constituents are Isoeugenol (43.28%), Beta-caryophyllene (35.61%), Gemacrene D (3.51%), Alpha- humulene (2.09%). Most of the identified compounds are biologically important. Plant has various properties such as antistress, antiseptic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, hypoglycemic, hypotensive, cardioprotective and antioxidant.

Keywords Ocimum Sanctum; Lamiaceae; Tulsi; Gas Chromatography; Mass Spectroscopy; Isoeugenol.

Introduction There are approximately 35,000 medicinal plants which are used for the therapeutic effect according to Ayurveda and siddha and unani and other traditional system. In which *Ocimum sanctum* is one of the most important of plant for medicinal purpose. It is employed in the treatment of various disease such as antimicrobial infection, antifungal, anticancer, arthritis, chronic fever, antifertility, eye disease, hepatoprotective, antispasmodic, and analgesic, antiemetic. Cardio protective.^[1] This medicinal herb have also been shown to reduce blood glucose levels, making it an effective treatment of diabetes.^[2]

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the major chemical constituents of essential oil of *Ocimum sanctum*.

Review of Literature Holy Basil (tulsi in Sanskrit) is an aromatic herb from the Lamiaceae family that has been used in Ayurvedic medicine for over 3000 years. It is native to the Indian subcontinent.^[3] Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum* L.), known as the "queen of herbs", is a plant that grows in portions of North and Eastern Africa, China, Hainan Island, and Taiwan.^[4] The tulsi plant is a bushy shrub or small tree native to the tropics and subtropics. It smells and tastes completely different from anything else. It reaches a mature height of three to five feet. When making Ayurvedic remedies, there are numerous preparations of *Ocimum* leaves, including Mahajvarankusa Rasa, Pancamrt Rasa, and Manasamitra Vataka. *Ocimum* is used in cold distillation, vegetable or pulse soup, refreshing beverages, Ghrit (medicinal ghee), medicinal powders, medicinal oil, Sheeta jwarantak vati (anti-malaria pills), and tulsi tea.^[5,6] The chemical composition of the *O. sanctum*, essential oil might vary depending upon the origins, environmental conditions, and types of cultivars.^[7,8] The antioxidant and other biological properties of the *O. sanctum* essential oils and extracts have been of great interest in both the academia and food industries because of their antioxidant and antimicrobial potentials. Even though few reports on the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of the *O. sanctum* essential oil and extracts are available separately.^[9] Physiological benefits of tulsi can be attributed to its ability to assist with the body's internal housekeeping and protection of the body from toxin-induced damage. These functions are often attributed to tulsi's high content of phenolic compounds and anti-oxidant properties, with Krishna tulsi (black/purple variety) having a higher phenolic content and anti-oxidant capacity than white Vana (wild) tulsi.^[10]

Methodology

Plant material- Fresh leaves of *O. Sanctum* were collected from Botanical Garden of Department of Botany, M.S.J. PG. College Bharatpur, Rajasthan.

Extraction and Preparation of Oil- Extraction of oil was carried out by standard Hydro-distillation method Clevenger's apparatus and all operations were carried out at room temperature. The crushed leaves and floral part was placed in a separate flask, together with distilled water (1 L). After 5-6 hours, oil was collected from the apparatus, anhydrous

with sodium sulphate from removal of water traces, then this 100% pure essential oil were dispended into dark bottle and stored at 4°C until used.

Gas chromatography-Quantitative analysis of the essential oil of *O. sanctum* was carried out using a Shimadzu GC- 2010. Nitrogen was used as carrier gas at 10 psi inlet pressure with FID and Omega SPTm column (30.0 m x 0.25 mm ID, film thickness 0.25 um). Injector and detector temperatures were 270°C and 280°C respectively. Column temperature programmed from 80°C (2 mins hold), 80°C to 180°C at 4°C/min and 180°C to 230°C at 6°C/min withhold time of 6 min and 19 min. respectively. The flow rate of carrier gas was 1.21 ml/min and split ratio was 1:80. The data were processed on GC solutions software for oil composition.

GC-MS Analyses-GC-MS data was obtained on a Shimadzu GCMS-QP-2010 plus system using Omega SPTm column (30.0 m x 0.25 mm ID. film thickness 0.25 um). Helium was used as carrier gas. Injector, Mass detector and Ion source temperatures were 270°C, 280°C and 250°C respectively. Column temperature programmed from 80°C (2 mins hold), 80°C to 180°C at 4°C/min and 180°C to 230°C at 6°C/min withhold time of 6 min and 19 min. respectively. The flow rate of carrier gas was 1.21 ml/min and split ratio was 1:80. EI source and mass range were 70 eV and 40-850 amu respectively. Compounds were identified by using Willey, NIST and Perfumery libraries.

Result and Discussion

The color and smell of oil is light yellow and intense scent respectively. The essential oil yield from the dried leaves has been reported from 0.07% to 0.7% by Valtcho *et al.*, 2008. [11]

The leaf of *O. sanctum* contains 0.7% volatile oil comprising about 71% eugenol and 20% methyl eugenol. The compounds present in the hydroalcolic extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* were identified by GC-MS analysis. The active principles with their retention time (RT), molecular weight (MW) and concentration (%) are presented in Table. 43 compounds were identified in hydroalcoholic extract by GC-MS. The major components present in leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* were Eugenol (43.28%), Caryophyllene (35.61), Germacrene D (3.51%), alpha-humulene (2.09%), trans beta ocimene (2.09%) (Table).

Table
Peak Report TIC

Peak#	R.Time	Area	Name%	Name
1	3.663	1366894	0.20	Cis-3-Hexenol
2	5.713	3643196	0.54	Alpha-pinene
3	6.189	3116078	0.46	Camphene
4	7.045	434544	0.06	Sabinene
5	7.152	1942648	0.29	Beta-pinene
6	7.298	437930	0.06	1-Octen-3-ol
7	7.694	1088439	0.16	Myrcene
8	7.901	259433	0.04	Ethyl-hexanol
9	8.164	613939	0.09	n-octanal
10	8.343	386784	0.06	Hex-(3 Z)-enyl acetate
11	8.990	241760	0.04	Para-cymene
12	9.154	4090838	0.60	Limonene
13	9.252	4823617	0.71	Eucalyptol
14	10.016	14201052	2.09	Trans-beta-ocimene
15	10.422	556147	0.08	Gamma-terpinene
16	11.690	690832	0.10	Terpinolene
17	12.268	7283979	1.07	Linalool
18	14.142	13296218	1.95	Camphor
19	15.168	6088711	0.89	Borneol
20	15.670	393847	0.06	4-Terpineol
21	16.310	596183	0.09	Alpha-terpineol
22	16.585	755073	0.11	Myrtenol
23	18.599	617902	0.09	Citral b
24	19.952	1006114	0.15	Geranial
25	21.495	1147641	0.17	Trans-methyl-Cinnamate
26	23.272	950624	0.14	Alpha-cubebene
27	24.192	294586384	43.28	Isoeugenol
28	24.456	4985642	0.73	Alpha-copaene
29	24.925	5976321	0.88	Methyl cinnamylate
30	25.073	1742052	0.26	Beta-cubebene
31	26.471	242364312	35.61	Beta-caryophyllene
32	26.778	1308847	0.19	Calarene
33	27.652	14192374	2.09	Alpha-humulene
34	28.799	23918803	3.51	Germacrene D
35	28.968	1839621	0.27	Beta-selinene
36	29.329	2976509	0.44	Alpha-selinene
37	30.485	2430624	0.36	Delta-cadinene
38	30.806	523272	0.08	Gamma-cis-bisabolene
39	31.259	285323	0.04	Alpha-cis-Bisabolene
40	32.144	3855950	0.57	Intermedeol
41	32.764	8768563	1.29	Caryophyllene oxide
42	33.104	546969	0.08	Viridiflorol
43	33.756	327124	0.05	Humulene epoxide II
		680659113	100.00	

Ocimum sanctum has various properties such as antistress, antiseptic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, hypoglycemic, hypotensive, cardioprotective and antioxidant [12] Eugenol (1-hydroxy-2-methoxy-4-allylbenzene), the active constituents present in *O. sanctum* have been found to be largely responsible for the therapeutic potentials.[13] The study reveals that various secondary metabolites such as carbohydrate, tannin, flavonoids, saponins, glycoside, terpenoid, fatty acids and phenol are present in tulsi leaf extract. Leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* contain water-soluble phenolic compounds and various other constituents, such as eugenol, methyl eugenol and caryophyllene that may act as an immunostimulant. Saponins act as anti-hyperlipidemic, hypotensive and cardio-depressive properties.[14] The phytochemical constituents such as alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols and several other aromatic compounds of plants serve a defense mechanism against predation by many microorganisms, insects and other herbivore[15] Glycosides can act as cardio-stimulants in cases of cardiac failure.[16] Tannins have anti diarrheal and haemostasis properties.[17] Flavanoids are responsible for antioxidant and immunostimulatory properties. Alkaloids, glycosides, flavanoids and saponins are antibiotic principles of plants and these antibiotic principles are actually the defensive mechanisms of the plants against pathogens.[18] Eugenol is reported to possess Antimycotic[19] Antiviral[20] Desinsection[21] Antiparasitic[22] Antioxidant[35] Anticancer[24] and Anthelmintic activities.[25]

Conclusion The constituents of essential oil isolated by hydro distillation of leaf parts of *Ocimum sanctum* was examined by Gas chromatography and Mass spectroscopy. 43 compounds accounting for 99.9% of oil were identified in leaf oil. The constituents are Isoeugenol (43.28%), Beta-caryophyllene (35.61%), Gemacrene-D (3.51%) , Alpha- humulene (2.09%).. The antioxidant and other biological properties of the *O. sanctum* essential oils and extracts have been of great interest in both the academia and food industries because of their antioxidant and antimicrobial potentials. Most of the identified compounds are biologically important and great use in medicinal purpose.

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